

CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES IN WORKING AS FOREIGN TEACHERS IN THE UNITED STATES: LIVED EXPERIENCES OF THE FILIPINO TEACHERS IN FOREIGN LAND

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Challenges and Opportunities in Working as Foreign Teachers in the United States: Lived Experiences of the Filipino Teachers in Foreign Land

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Abstract

While studies about teachers' experiences in US is growing, no study was ever conducted among the rising population of Filipino teachers in the Florida district schools. This study generally aims to demystify and understand the lived experiences of selected Filipino teachers in terms of challenges, opportunities, and coping strategies while teaching in the foreign land. A pure qualitative and case study research design was employed. A total of five (5) Filipino teachers who have stayed in US for at least two years were purposively sampled. Statements and responses are thematically analyzed. Results showed that significantly better compensation and benefits, strong school support, and positive work-life balance are experienced opportunities relative to the previous encounters in the Philippines. On the other note, challenges are also evident in trade to the identified opportunities. Majority of the respondents grappled from emotional, psychological, and physical stress due to tough adjustments from culture and worsened by homesickness. Remarkably, building connections with the Filipino community support and constant communication with families are effective coping strategies that made the respondents succeed in US for at least two (2) years. It is further noted that no respondent has mentioned about Philippine government support inspite of the economic contribution of OFWs. Findings in this paper are significant information for benchmark and are potential inputs for policy development.

Keywords: *florida district schools, filipino teachers, challenges, opportunities, coping strategies*

Introduction

The number of Filipinos who migrated and worked as teachers in other countries continues to grow in search for better economic opportunities. Uytico and Abadiano (2020) asserted that high unemployment rates and low wages in the Philippines are strong driving forces that compel teachers to search for greener economic and living conditions in other countries. Highlighted in a news article written by Santos (2023) of the Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS), the Alliance of Concerned Teachers (ACT) mentioned that teachers in public or private schools in the Philippines are underpaid. ACT said that there is a shortage of 147,000 teachers in Philippine public schools. Statistics from the Philippine Overseas Employment Administration (POEA) show that from 2013 to 2017, an average of 1,500 teachers left annually to work abroad. In addition, Bersales (2017) and the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) bulletin 2017 underscored that many

Filipinos are living below the poverty line, with a high unemployment rate of 5.6% and a staggering underemployment rate of 16.3%. Undeniably, the sacrifices of Filipino teachers abroad contributed to countries development. Remittances, is one of the most direct and significant contributions to the Philippine economy. Filipino teachers working overseas often send part of their earnings back home to support their families. These remittances are a vital source of income for many households and contribute to the overall economic stability of the Philippines (Alonzo, 2022). A press release from PIDS by Albert and Tabuga (2024) emphasized the remittances of the Overseas Filipino Workers (OFWs) account to nearly 10% of the country's GDP. Arguably, by working abroad, Filipino teachers help alleviate some of the employment pressure within the Philippines, especially in fields where there may be a surplus of graduates. This can contribute to a more balanced labor market at home (Chua, 2021).

While it is clear that higher salary is the major and topmost reason that explains the migration of teachers abroad, compromises and challenges are undeniable. Lee et al. (2015) found that many Filipino teachers suffer from emotional, psychological, and physical stress while adapting to the host countries. More particularly in the United States, Piccio (2019) noted that vast of Filipinos have grappled from homesickness, cultural differences, discrimination, and accent and language problems. In spite of the evident challenges of teaching abroad, an increasing number of Filipino migrants who decided to teach in US remained unstoppable. Arguably, these migrants spend thousands of dollars and risk being victims of human trafficking just to be able to teach in the United States (Perea, 2018).

Definitely, both the risks and the benefits of working as a teacher in the United States and other countries are well-documented in the literature. However, little is known about the experiences of the surging quantity of Filipinos who are teaching in the district schools of Florida. Subscribing to the contention of a press release from PIDS Albert and Tabuga (2024), this study supports that policymakers beyond remittances and address the complex social and emotional implications of labor migration. By demystifying and understanding the lived experiences of the teachers, policies and support programs will be tailored to the needs of Filipino teachers.

Research Questions

More specifically, this study aimed to answer the following research questions.

1. What are the opportunities experienced by the Filipino teachers in the United States which made them stay at the foreign land?
2. What are the challenges experienced by the Filipino teachers in the United States in trade for the opportunities?

3. What are the coping mechanisms, including its sources, that made Filipino teachers sustain in the teaching profession at the foreign land?

Methodology

A case study design was used to document the lived experiences of the Filipino teachers who are currently and actively teaching in the public schools of Florida district in the United States. Such design is deemed appropriate in the study considering its general objective of unfolding the lived experiences of selected teachers. A total of five (5) teachers who have been teaching in US for at least two (2) years were interviewed. A set of guide questions were patterned according to the research objectives. Moreover, data collected were analyzed using the commonly used thematic analysis.

Results and Discussion

Relevant findings from the interview are presented with respect to the sequence of the research questions. Furthermore, guided with the research questions, the lived experiences of the teachers are thematically grouped according to opportunities, challenges, and coping mechanisms.

Opportunities Experienced by the Filipino Teachers in Florida District

To be a teacher in the Florida opens an ample of opportunities. All respondents have repeatedly mentioned that the kind of school support they received in Florida district schools are far different from the schools in their home country. Instructional resources are readily available, technological facilities are adequate and advanced, and other supplementary tools are secured in the classrooms. Teachers mostly enter the classrooms with all instructional materials in place which provides more time for subject preparations and classroom management. This is very contrary to the experiences of the teachers in many public schools in the Philippines where teachers struggle financially from the inadequacy of instructional resources, facilities, and technological equipment (Bai, 2023). In an interview with one of the respondents, one of the teachers stated that;

When it comes to opportunities, there are many factors that encourage Filipino teachers to stay and work in the U.S. Nearly all instructional needs are met, with resources such as instructional materials, learning materials, and supplementary tools readily available. This support significantly eases the teaching process and reduces the time and effort teachers must spend on lesson preparation. -Teacher A

Such kind of prerogative for teachers results to better approaches in teaching, increase in performance, and even professional growth. In addition, Zheng et al. (2015) noted that the educational system and support in US promotes good work-life balance and better wellbeing. This is entirely different in the Philippines where most teachers are forced to spend beyond office hours, even holidays and weekends, yet receiving constant number of benefits (Azevedo et al., 2022). As shown in table 1, access to positive instructional support from school is the first relevant theme that signifies for an opportunity of being a Filipino teacher in US.

Table 1. *Opportunities experienced by the Filipino teachers*

<i>Codes</i>	<i>No. of Times Repeated</i>	<i>Categories</i>	<i>Themes</i>
Greener Pasture	5	Economic privileges	Significantly Higher Salary
Good compensation	5		
Financial security	5		
Adequacy of instructional resources	5	Educational and School Support	Provisions of adequate instructional resources
Availability of advanced technological facilities	5		
High-quality classroom infrastructure	5		
Learning new culture	5	Career development and learning experiences	Professional growth and development
Broadening perspectives to quality education	4		
Communication and language immersion	3		

Table 1 further highlights that the significantly bigger salary in US compared to the Philippines is a rare opportunity that a teacher enjoys and in fact the major reason why all the respondents have decided to migrate and teach in US. Such monetary privilege is indicated in the statement of one of the respondents who said;

“In terms of salary, there is a significant difference between the compensation of teachers in the Philippines and those working in the U.S. Teachers in the U.S. are well-compensated and also receive insurance benefits, which is a major factor that motivates educators to remain and work in countries like the U.S.” -Teacher B

Consistent to many studies in the literature, the statement from teacher B provides supplemental empirical evidence regarding the greener pasture and better economic opportunities in working abroad, more particularly in US (Reyes et al., 2020). Higher wages with more benefits are confirmed as major reasons that urged teachers to leave from the professional oath.

Professional growth and development also emerge as a significant theme that describes the opportunity of being a teacher in a foreign

country. Bridgstock (2009) similarly reported that US provides access to wide options of career growth and development programs which are essential to skills enhancement. Substantiating the claim about opportunities for career growth, one of the respondents said; *“Immersing myself in a diverse cultural environment has been incredibly enriching, broadening my perspectives and enhancing my teaching experience” -Teacher C*

Testimonies from teacher C speak of the programs and trainings that are provided to all teachers in US. Exposure to such highly effective seminars and capability building activities are essential to the promotion of classroom management skills and overall teaching performance. Moreover, Akiba and LeTendre (2009) found that many teachers in US are able to manage their post graduate degrees because of the flexibility of work schedules. Depending possible in the region, many teaching positions in the US offer a work-life balance with structured schedules, including summers off, which can be a significant benefit and implication for schooling.

Challenges Experienced by the Filipino Teachers in Florida District

Behind the opportunities of the being a teacher in US, sacrifices and challenges remained undeniable. Homesickness is the worst emotional and psychological enemy of the Filipino teachers. Campomanes (2005) described that most of the Filipino teachers who worked abroad have gone through misery and nostalgia from home. Leaving far away from family is an extraordinary grapple of adjustment, while some can't even survive (Rosales, 2024). Definitely, being away from the family is a roller coaster ride of emotion that each teacher should overcome to succeed in a teaching career in US or even in other country. As shown in table 2, homesickness, adjustment to new culture, new language and routine, and feeling strange from a community resulted to the emergence of the emotional and psychological adjustment as the first thematic challenges experienced by the Filipino teachers. Many studies also reveal similar findings about the extraordinary adjustments hurdled by vast Filipino teachers not only in US but even in other foreign land (Rosales, 2024). These relevant results only indicate that emotional and psychological struggles are part of the big trade offs against the economic opportunities and other positive benefits.

The standard of educational system in US is far different from the Philippines. Fitting into these differences can be so challenging and may take longer time of endurance and adjustment. As presented in table 2. Adjustment to the new educational landscape emerges as the second relevant theme that describes the challenges experienced by the respondents. Gomez-Lange (2024) noted that new foreign teachers mostly encountered tough adjustment from the cultural diversity of the students, language differences, and classroom rules because of being unfamiliar from a very strange classroom environment.

Table 2. *Challenges experienced by the Filipino teachers*

<i>Codes</i>	<i>No. of Times Repeated</i>	<i>Categories</i>	<i>Themes</i>
Homesickness	5	Misery from home	Psychological and emotional adjustment
Nostalgia from family routines	5		
Cultural adjustment	5	Adjustment to the new environment	
Feeling strange from the new community	5		
Language adjustment	4		
Handling Students' differences	5	Unfamiliarity to the new classroom environment	Adjustment to the new educational landscape
Adjustment to classroom dynamics	5		
Overwhelmed from the new technology and tools	5	Adjustment to resources and curriculum expectations	
High standard of curriculum and assessment	4		

In addition, hailing from a developing country, most of the Filipino teachers are overwhelmed from the advanced technological resources, high standard curriculum, and assessments. Such scenarios are particularly indicated in the statement from one of the teachers who said;

“Filipino teachers in the U.S. often face significant challenges. Handling students in a different cultural and educational environment can be difficult, as classroom dynamics and expectations vary. Navigating new teaching tools and technologies can also be overwhelming, especially when adapting to a different system. Homesickness adds to the emotional strain, as being far from family and familiar surroundings makes the adjustment even harder” . -Teacher D

Vast studies in the literature show coherence to the findings presented above particularly regarding the serious adjustments from the high educational standards in US (Modesto, 2020). Accordingly, these challenges are essential elements of a successful teaching career in US and also in other foreign countries (Modesto, 2020; Gomez-Lange, 2024).

Coping Mechanisms of the Filipino Teachers In spite of the Challenges

Coping mechanisms are very essential in addressing the challenges of being Filipino teacher in US. Table 3 exposes some of the coping strategies which made the respondents stayed in the teaching profession for at least two (2) years. Establishing support from a community and drawing constant support from families and close friends via online platform are the thematic areas that describe the coping mechanisms of the respondents to surpass the emotional, psychological, and physical pressures of being a teacher in the foreign country.

Table 3. *Coping mechanisms of the Filipino teachers amidst challenges*

<i>Codes</i>	<i>No. of Times Repeated</i>	<i>Categories</i>	<i>Themes</i>
Building connections with fellow Filipino workers	5	Belongingness in a support community	Establishing support from a new community
Creating friends with other people	5		
Constant communication with family	5	Family and peer support	Drawing constant support from families and close friends virtually
Constant virtual meeting with peers and close friends	5		

As displayed in table 3, all respondents consistently mentioned that the exerted efforts to build connections with fellow Filipino workers and even developed friendships with other people to ensure belongingness in the very new and strange community. Macapagong et al. (2023) found out that Filipino community support in other countries is getting stronger and visible. Getting connected with such organization is an effective source of strength and comfort while in the middle of adjustment process. Modesto (2020) also noted that to be with co-Filipino workers can lighten the emotional burden especially when conversation is dominated with the use of the native language. The ability to mingle with other people is an asset to the success of career in US and other countries. Being teachable and with high willingness to learn from the pioneers is a very helpful attitude to endure the hardships of being far away from the comfort zone.

Further, virtual supports from family and close peers are also spotted as major sources of courage and tenacity while struggling from homesickness and emotional adjustment. Best et al. (2014) emphasized the huge advantage of social media platforms in facilitating communication with families and peers. Relative to the interviews conducted, getting in touched with the family and friends from outside countries was very helpful in their adjustment process. In particular, one of the respondents said;

“Yes exactly. Constant communication with families and friends during my first months of stay here in US was so instrumental to my status today. I felt the burden of homesickness and emotional shocks, but I was able to win those foes through the strong virtual support from my family and closest friends from the Philippines”. -Teacher E

At a closer look to the coping strategies divulged by the respondents, it is noticeable that there is no mention of government support from the Philippines inspite of the economic contribution of the Filipino workers through remittances. Definitely, besides the information and insights provided in this present study, one of its significant implications is the call for wellness program that might be sponsored by the Philippine government in protecting the OFWs, and thereby sustaining economic benefits.

Conclusions

In light of the discussions above, it is found out that the lived experiences of the Filipino teachers in the Florida district schools are mixed with opportunities and challenges. In particular, the study concludes the following.

Filipino teachers enjoyed significantly higher economic benefits and better living conditions in the Florida district schools. The evidently higher salary compared in the Philippines, the overwhelming instructional support, and the positive work-life balance due to structured work schedule are the major drivers that made the Filipino teachers stayed in US.

Experiences of the teachers also include inevitable psychological, emotional, and physical challenges in exchange to the luring benefits. These are serious hurdles where some, though small in number, failed to surpass.

Inspite of the challenges, the strong Filipino community support system and constant conversation with the family are instrumental to the success of the career of the teachers in Florida. In addition, the study calls for a supplemental support from the Philippine government that might be in a form of psychosocial enhancing program to sustain the successful career of OFWs and thereby improve economic returns. Along with this, it is recommended that the government may legislate and implement policies that provide holistic assistance that is instrumental to the development of better well-being among Filipino teachers abroad.

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